

D8.4 – First report on digital and printed dissemination, exploitation and communication material

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List of Abbreviations

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
API	Application Programming Interface
CFA	Climate Farm Advisor
CFD	Climate Farm Demo
CSF	Climate Smart Farming
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
M	Month
NC	National Coordinator
PDF	Pilot Demo Farm
WP	Work Package

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Abstract

Deliverable D8.4 – First report on digital and printed dissemination, exploitation and communication material presents all material developed during the first 12 months of project implementation, with an aim of ensuring consistency in communication efforts, attracting relevant stakeholders and promoting the project and its ambition.

The report elaborates on the various tools and channels employed to support all partners in their DEC activities. One of its objectives is also to empower all project partners by equipping them with a comprehensive understanding of these tools, enabling them to effectively convey the project's message and engage with the target audience. The report thus sets a foundation for continued refinement and enhancement of communication plan, ensuring a lasting impact in advancing climate-resilient agricultural practices.

1. Introduction

Climate Farm Demo (CFD) is a unique pan-European network of Pilot Demo Farmers (PDFs) covering 27 countries and all pedo-climatic areas. Its overall aim is to accelerate the adoption of Climate Smart Farming (CSF) practices and solutions by farmers and all actors of the Climate Smart Agriculture Knowledge & Innovation Systems (AKIS), with a view of adapting agricultural production systems to climate change and of achieving a carbon neutral agricultural sector by 2050, thereby meeting the targets of the EU Climate strategy. To reach this objective, the project adopts a Multi-Actor approach by connecting 1,500 Pilot Demo Farmers and their Climate Farm Advisors (CFAs) at European and national levels to increase knowledge exchange & cross-fertilisation in their respective AKIS. Technical and social innovations covering a broad range of thematic areas will be demonstrated to the wider farming community across six annual demo campaigns (4,500 demo-events) supporting interactive and peer-to-peer learning.

The present deliverable showcases all the communication materials (digital and printed) developed for CFD in the first year of the project. At the end of the project, in M84, WP will produce *D8.11 – Final report on digital and printed dissemination, exploitation and communication material*.

The document is divided into chapters in the following way:

- *Chapter 1 – Introduction* offers a short overview of the project, the present deliverable and the document structure.
- *Chapter 2 – Visual Identity* is about the visual standards that all the content related to CFD needs to meet.
- *Chapter 3 – Project Website* describes the official CFD website and its main functionalities.
- *Chapter 4 – CFD Social Media Profiles* focuses on the project's social media presence and performance so far.
- *Chapter 5 – General Project Flyer* shows what kind of material was designed to offer essential CFD information in the form of a brochure, suitable for different kinds of promotion.
- *Chapter 6 – Infographics* describes charts and diagrams designed to provide the basic information about CFD (network, impact, solutions, etc.)
- *Chapter 7 – Project Poster* demonstrates the poster designed to represent the core of CFD.
- *Chapter 8 – Project Flag & Rollup* presents different variations of flag and rollup materials that can be used to promote CFD.
- *Chapter 9 – Leaflet for Farmers* is about a short flyer created to facilitate the farmer registration process, as well as for use at conferences, fairs, etc.
- *Chapter 10 – Newsletters* describes two different kinds of newsletters about the project (internal and external).
- *Chapter 11 – Email Signature*
- *Chapter 12 – Next Steps* is about plans and efforts that need to follow everything done so far in order to continue successful dissemination and communication.

2. Visual Identity

Early in the project, WP8 developed the CFD Corporate Identity Manual (described in detail in *D8.1 – Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan at EU & National Levels*). The manual aims to describe the project's visual identity and guide the partners in terms of the proper use the CFD logo, official colours, and various kinds of document templates.

Climate Farm Demo – Corporate Identity Manual

Index

1. The Logo
2. Corporate Colours
3. Typography and Font
4. Logo Size
5. Logo Protection Zone
6. Logo Versions
7. Logo Over an Image or Photo
8. Examples of Bad Logo Usage

Climate Farm Demo – Corporate Identity Manual

5. Logo Protection Zone

The logo's perimeter must be protected by creating a "clean zone" that prevents "invasive" elements from getting close.

Climate Farm Demo – Corporate Identity Manual

7. Logo Over an Image or Photo

We will follow the criteria:

- Colour version only if the background allows it
- Monochromatic white or black if the final result is clearly readable after applying over the background
- Monochromatic white with a black box if the result is unreadable without it

Figure 1. Excerpt from the Visual Identity Manual

A short summary of said content is available in the following sub-chapters.

2.1 CFD Logo

Given the main focus of CFD (promoting CSF practices through the network of PDFs and CFAs), the project logo (see figure below) was created to represent the way in which agriculture, technology, and climate action are interlinked. The semi-circular lines, their colours, and positions symbolise that.

Figure 2. CFD logo

The visual identity guidelines explain the correct ways to use the logo (the minimal size, selecting different versions based on the background colour, and so forth) and typography requirements (fonts).

In addition, all the partners are informed that dissemination materials need to showcase the logo, as well as the EU emblem and a statement about received funding from the Horizon Europe program.

2.1.1 FarmDemo Logo Redesign

When speaking about the CFD logo, it is important to point out its background, i.e., FarmDemo. It was established by these three related projects: NEFERTITI, PLAID and AgriDemoF2F. Moreover, in 2021, IPM WORKS joined the FarmDemo family, which continues to expand with CFD. Still, with new projects starting and previous ones finishing, the focus and reasoning behind the farm demo idea also evolves, hence the need to freshen up the visual identity. The new FarmDemo logo has a modernised appearance thanks to a new typeface and a more open and stylised sign, symbolising a knowledge flow from FarmDemo to other projects and from projects outside FarmDemo to those in the family.

Figure 3. New and old logotypes

2.2 Corporate Colours

The project colour palette features different shades of green and orange/yellow – these are commonly associated with nature and found in it. Graphic elements built around the CFD brand should use this colour combination whenever possible.

Figure 4. CFD corporate colours

2.3 Document Templates

Templates in various formats were developed early in the project with the necessary visual elements. CFD partners can find it in the project's designated workspace (MS Teams). This includes the following:

- Deliverable template
- Milestone template
- Working document template
- Meeting agenda template
- Meeting minutes template
- PPT presentation template

Title of the document in two or more lines

Subtitle in one line – optional – 2nd level

14 January 2023

Author(s):
 Name Surname, ORGANISATION ACRONYM

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060212.

Meeting Name

Date:	Time:
Place:	
Organiser:	
Meeting with:	

Agenda

[time] [subject]

This project has received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101060212.

Funded by the European Union

Click to add title

Click to add subtitle

Author

Figure 5. CFD template examples

3. Project Website

The project website (climatefarmdemo.eu) was designed and launched under *D8.2 – Online content repository (knowledge reservoir)* and *D8.3 – Project Website*, thus allowing WP8 to mark Milestone 74 (*Website is online and operational*) as achieved in M6. The website is a common public space presenting all the important aspects of CFD. Interested parties can thus be informed about the project objectives, ongoing activities and upcoming ones, etc. The development of the website is based on a user needs & requirements assessment performed during first two months of the project, as well as experience accumulated through NEFERTITI (GA No 772705), since it is a CFD predecessor.

Figure 6. CFD website homepage

Apart from the homepage, the project website also contains the following segments:

- Informative pages (About page, WPs & Deliverables, Consortium, Advisory Board, Thematic Areas, Living Labs, News, Newsletters, Webinars, Practice Abstracts, etc.)
- Demonstration Farms pages (to map and present all Demonstration Farms recruited – Pilot Demo Farms, Experimental Farms and Lighthouse Farms)
- Demonstration Events pages (to list all Demo Events registered and offer an overview of learning opportunities)
- Solutions Repository pages (a place for all adaptation & mitigation climate solutions, tools, guidelines and methods)

Through feedback from the key project members, the site can be upgraded and updated regularly. Some of the important updates are the translation to all EU languages, responsiveness to all devices (mobile and tablet in addition to desktop/laptop) and interoperability with other platforms, after the CFD online infrastructure gathers enough valuable data to be shared, most probably via API, with topic-related projects and its platforms.

Finally, there will be an annual website review, allowing for visual refreshments and incremental upgrades. Any major visual refreshment will be implemented according to the visual identity standards described earlier or according to future Executive Committee decisions.

4. CFD Social Media Profiles

In M6, WP8 submitted a thorough social media strategy for CFD within *D8.1 – Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan at EU & National Levels*. Over the last decade, social media networks have become essential in terms of raising project awareness, disseminating information and engaging with relevant audiences. We must underline that CFD is still in its early stage, given that the project duration is 84 months, and many project activities and concrete results are yet to come. Therefore, the impact of social media is expected to be higher later on.

The following sub-chapters focus on the four main platforms we rely on to achieve the objectives set in the strategy. We use them to attract farmers, advisors, policy makers, economic actors of the supply chain, representatives of academia and research institutions, and society at large.

4.1 X (Twitter)

The project account on X (known as Twitter up until recently) is found at @ClimateFarmDemo.

Figure 7. CFD X (Twitter) profile and post example

We use Twitter to spread short messages and pieces of news, relying on relevant hashtags to boost post visibility. Some basic X (Twitter) analytics can be seen in the table below.

Table 1. CFD X (Twitter) performance

CFD on X (Twitter)	
Link to profile	https://twitter.com/ClimateFarmDemo
Number of followers (on the day of writing this report)	161
Number of posts	85
Average impressions per post	199

4.2 LinkedIn

The project is also active on LinkedIn, as illustrated in the Figure below. LinkedIn's capacity for lengthier posts, unlike X (Twitter), grants our social media team the opportunity to share more in-depth information. Leveraging this capability, we will effectively share project results among LinkedIn community.

Figure 8. CFD LinkedIn profile & post example

LinkedIn allows sharing longer posts compared to X (Twitter); hence the social media team can share more information here. That could be the reason why this profile has managed to attract more followers compared to X.

Table 2. CFD LinkedIn performance

CFD on LinkedIn	
Link to profile	https://www.linkedin.com/company/climatefarmdemo/

Number of followers (on the day of writing this report)	371
Number of posts	70
Average impressions per post	405

4.3 Facebook

The project Facebook page was created somewhat later compared to other CFD social media accounts, following a short survey that WP8 prepared to see whether it was necessary to utilise platforms other than the most common ones, i.e., Twitter (now X) and LinkedIn. Since the results suggested that Facebook was used by farmers quite widely, the WP8 team created this page.

Figure 9. CFD Facebook profile & post example

Since the Facebook page was launched slightly later, as described above, the numbers are expected to be lower compared to other social media profiles at this point in time. Since Facebook is a network that we will primarily use for promoting demo events across Europe, we expect to see its full potential during demonstration campaigns which start next year.

Table 3. CFD Facebook performance

CFD on Facebook	
Link to profile	https://www.facebook.com/climatefarmdemo/
Number of followers (on the day of writing this report)	53
Number of posts	19
Average impressions per post	44

4.4 YouTube

All videos created by the project will be uploaded to the FarmDemo channel on YouTube, also used by the RUR-11 projects PLAID, AgriDemo F2F and NEFERTITI. This means an additional boost for the potential of CFD videos since the channel is already well-established, with around 1,730 subscribers.

At the moment, there are no CFD-related videos uploaded to the platform because the relevant activities are yet to begin. Once there are such videos, they will be further shared on other social media channels (X, LinkedIn, and Facebook) since it is a great way to attract more viewers.

Figure 10. FarmDemo YouTube channel

5. General Project Flyer

Figure 11. General CFD flyer

6. Infographics

Infographics have been crafted to convey essential details and fundamental information about CFD, simplifying intricate concepts for easy comprehension. These infographics encompass partner details, anticipated impact, climate smart farming solutions, and other pertinent project information, as illustrated below.

EXAMPLE OF NATIONAL NETWORK

AKIS REPRESENTATION

Figure 13. CFD infographics

7. Project Poster

Having a project poster is important because it enables on to use graphics and text to present a project in a way that is visually interesting and accessible. This can be very helpful at fairs, conferences, exhibitions, and similar gatherings. Similar to the general brochure, PPP, and some of the infographic, the poster features the information about project aims, scope and areas of influence.

Figure 14. CFD project poster

8. Project Flag & Rollup

Much like previously described branding materials, having a flag and a rollup representing the project is an effective way to offer a broad view of CFD. It allows target audiences to easily recognise project representatives and interact with them. The main occasions in which flags and/or rollups are used are organisation of the public events (presentations, workshops, farm demonstrations), but also participation of project partners to various topic-related events such as agricultural fairs and exhibitions, conferences, or similar. The following figures show the different versions of these materials.

Figure 15. CFD flags

Figure 16. CFD rollups

9. Leaflet for Farmers

A flyer for informing farmers about the project and opportunities for them was designed (Figure 11) and translated in all 27 languages of the project. It is to be used by National Coordinators and advisors during the farm recruiting process, or by PDFs for a portion of demonstration activities, as well as in European context – various events, synergies with other projects, etc.

Figure 17. Leaflet for farmers

10. Newsletters

WP8 creates and sends out newsletters to offer the latest updates regarding project progress, activities and available results. There are two sorts of project newsletters – internal, provided to Consortium members, and external, meant for audiences outside the project. Therefore, the internal version provides CFD partners with concise information about the overall progress, ongoing and upcoming activities, new tools and more. The external CFD newsletter serves to build relationships with relevant stakeholders, boost social media following, disseminate results, etc. There is a subscription form on the project website allowing anyone to sign up for the external newsletter.

The task involving newsletters is entrusted to the BioSense Institute, managing it via the Mailchimp service, with contributions by Executive Committee members and other project partners when relevant. The language used is English, but NCs are welcome to translate the content to the local language and disseminate it further on their channels.

The total number of newsletters is 56. So far, three external newsletters and one internal newsletter have been sent. This is due to the fact that most activities were in very early stages, thus making it difficult to report in it in a way that is required for newsletter editions. However, the team is now accelerating newsletter preparation, and new issues will be sent frequently.

Welcome to the Horizon Europe project
Climate Farm Demo
Newsletter #1

**Do you want to learn more about
our project and activities?**

Keep reading!

Figure 18. CFD newsletter

11. Email Signature

An email banner in a signature is designed to enable representatives of partnering organisations consistently communicate their involvement in the project. Designed in two colours combinations email signature allows everyone to choose depending on preference, but also other communication elements they are involving in their email signature, such as logotype of the organisation or other projects they are engaged with. This banner not only reinforces the project's identity but also creates a professional and consistent image across all project-related communications including every email correspondence.

Figure 19. Email signature

12. Next Steps

Moving forward, our communication efforts will continue to evolve and expand in the forthcoming years. We remain committed to an inclusive approach, actively seeking and valuing feedback from our partners to ascertain their specific needs from WP8 for engaging a critical mass of stakeholders within their respective communities.

The creation of new communication materials will always respond to the dynamic of the project. Among first sets of materials in the upcoming period will be the development of a new document and presentation templates, strategically designed to highlight synergies with PIPs in Work Package 7. Moreover, we are gearing up for an extensive production of multimedia materials. As we progress into demonstration campaigns, multimedia assets will play a pivotal role in illustrating and promoting climate-smart agricultural practices. These engaging and informative materials will be uploaded to FarmDemo YouTube channel and serve as valuable tools in reaching a broader audience and encouraging the adoption of sustainable farming techniques.

By actively adapting and innovating our communication strategies, we are poised to effectively communicate upcoming project activities and disseminate results, maximizing the impact and reach of the Climate Farm Demo project.

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